

**ELITA GANDBOLCHILARIDA BA'ZI JISMONIY TAYYORGARLIK
PARAMETRLARI O'RTASIDAGI MUNOSABATLARNI TEKSHIRISH.**

Yarasheva Dilnoza

Buxoro Davlat Universiteti

Sport Faoliyati va Pedagogika Fakulteti

Sport faoliyati kafedrası

Tayanch Doktorant (Phd)

Email: d.i.yarasheva@buxdu.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10999628>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi gandbolchilarning sprint tezligi, reaksiya vaqtlari, kuch va vertikal sakrash xususiyatlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik o'rganiladi. Yoshi, bo'yi, vazni, sprint tezligi, reaksiya vaqti, kuch va vertikal sakrash qiymatlari asboblar bilan o'lchandi. Xususiyatlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni tekshirish uchun Pearson mahsulot korrelyatsiyasi testi qo'llanildi va muhim daraja $p < 0,05$ deb qabul qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: Qo'l to'pi, jismoniy tayyorgarlik, ishlash, korrelyatsiyasi testi.

**INVESTIGATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOME PARAMETERS OF
PHYSICAL TRAINING IN ELITE HANDBALL PLAYERS.**

Abstract. The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between sprint speed, reaction times, strength and vertical jump characteristics of handball players. Age, height, weight, sprint speed, reaction time, strength and vertical jump values were measured with instruments. Pearson's product correlation test was used to examine the relationship between characteristics and the significant level was taken as $p < 0.05$.

Key words: Handball, physical training, performance, correlation test.

**ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ВЗАИМОСВЯЗИ НЕКОТОРЫХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ
ПОДГОТОВКИ У ВЫСОКОКВАЛИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ ГАНДБОЛИСТОВ.**

Аннотация. Целью данного исследования является изучение взаимосвязи между скоростью спринта, временем реакции, силовыми и вертикальными прыжковыми характеристиками гандболистов. С помощью приборов измерялись возраст, рост, вес, скорость спринта, время реакции, сила и значения вертикального прыжка. Для изучения взаимосвязи между характеристиками использовался тест корреляции продуктов Пирсона, а уровень значимости принимался за $p < 0,05$.

Ключевые слова: Гандбол, физическая подготовка, результативность, корреляционный тест.

Kirish

Jismoniy tayyorgarlik deganda harakatlarning to'g'ri bajarilishi va jismoniy chidamlilik bilan bog'liq holda tananing hozirgi holati tushuniladi. Ushbu ta'rifga ko'ra, eng yuqori jismoniy tayyorgarlikka ega bo'lgan odam eng uzoq vaqt charchamasdan harakat qila oladigan odamdır.

Jismoniy tayyorgarlikni faoliyatni muvaffaqiyatli bajarish qobiliyati sifatida ham aniqlash mumkin. Jismoniy tayyorgarlik yurak-nafas olish tizimining chidamliligi, mushaklarning chidamliligi, mushaklarning kuchi, mushaklar kuchi, tezlik, moslashuvchanlik, chaqqonlik, muvozanat, reaksiya vaqti va tana tuzilishini o'z ichiga oladi. Bu sifatlar sport ko'rsatkichlari va

salomatlik nuqtai nazaridan har xil ahamiyatga ega bo'lganligi sababli, ular mahorat bilan bog'liq jismoniy tayyorgarlik va sog'liq bilan bog'liq jismoniy tayyorgarlik deb ataladi. Jismoniy va fiziologik tayyorgarlik sportda muvaffaqiyat qozonish uchun zarurdir.

Agar sportchining jismoniy va fiziologik xususiyatlari sport sohasiga mos bo'lmasa, kerakli sport ko'rsatkichiga to'liq erishib bo'lmaydi. Biroq, jismoniy tayyorgarlik yuqori ishlashning yagona muhim sharti emas. Sportdagi natijalarga ta'sir qiluvchi ba'zi jismoniy omillar bo'y, tana vazni, tana tarkibi, aerob va anaerob kuch, kuch, tezlik va moslashuvchanlikdir (Kalyon, 1990). Jismoniy tuzilma yuqori darajada ishlash uchun zarur bo'lgan xususiyatlardan biridir. Kuch, kuch, moslashuvchanlik, tezlik, chidamlilik va chaqqonlik kabi boshqa ishlash o'zgaruvchilari bilan birlashtirib ishlashga ijobiy ta'sir qiladi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi gandbolchilarda sprint tezligi, reaksiya vaqti, kuch va vertikal sakrash xususiyatlari o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni o'rganishdir.

1 usul

Sportchilarning o'lchovlari musobaqa davrida va dam olish kunlarida amalga oshiriladi.

Tana vazni 0,1 kg aniqlikdagi elektron tarozi bilan, balandligi esa 0,01 sm aniqlikdagi raqamli balandlik o'lchagich bilan o'lchanadi (Tamer, 2000). Tana massasi indeksini aniqlash uchun tana massasi indeksi = Tana vazni / Balandligi (m)² formulasidan foydalaniladi. 30 metrlik Sprint tezligi testi 0,01 sezgirlikdagi fotoelementni sinovning boshlanish va tugash nuqtalariga oldindan belgilangan 30 m maydonda joylashtirish va dam olish oralig'i bilan 2 ta sinovdan eng yaxshisini olish orqali o'tkazildi.

Qo'lni ushlab turish kuchi (o'ng va chap), orqa kuch va oyoq kuchi o'lchovlari orqa va oyoq dinamometrlari bilan amalga oshirildi. Vertikal sakrash testi vertikal sakrash taxtasi yordamida amalga oshirildi. Oyoqlar birgalikda va tana tik holatda, ikkala qo'l yuqoriga ko'tarilib, barmoq uchlari tegib turgan oxirgi nuqta belgilandi. Keyin, bor kuchi bilan ikki oyog'i bilan yuqoriga sakrab, taxtaga tegadi, bir qadam tashlamasdan va tizzalarini 90 gradus egmasdan sakrashni amalga oshirdi.

Bu jarayon ikki marta takrorlandi va eng yaxshi qiymat qayd etildi. Ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish: Tadqiqotda olingan barcha ma'lumotlar aniqlanadi. Olingan ma'lumotlarning o'rtacha arifmetik va standart og'ish qiymatlarini hisoblab chiqqandan so'ng, jismoniy tayyorgarlik qiymatlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni tekshirish uchun Pearson korrelyatsiya testi qo'llanildi va ahamiyatlilik darajasi $p < 0,05$ sifatida qabul qilindi.

Topilmalar

Ushbu tadqiqot gandbolchilarda sprint tezligi, reaksiya vaqti, kuch va vertikal sakrash xususiyatlari o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni o'rganish uchun o'tkaziladi. Ushbu tadqiqotni barcha elita gandbolchiga test va o'lchovlar qo'llanilsa bo'ladi. Barcha qiymatlar statistik tahlil qilinadi.

Munozara va xulosa

Ushbu tadqiqot gandbolchilarda sprint tezligi, reaksiya vaqti, kuch va vertikal sakrash xususiyatlari o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni o'rganish uchun o'tkaziladi. Tadqiqotda qatnashgan elita gandbolchilarning o'rtacha yoshi inobatga olinadi. Ularning yoshi, o'rtacha bo'yi sm, vazni kg, tana massasi indeksi yozib jadvalda joylashtiriladi.

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, gandbolchilarning jismoniy tayyorgarligining ko'plab parametrlari o'zaro bog'liq va gandbolchilarning o'rtacha ko'rsatkichlari adabiyot

tadqiqotlari bilan solishtirganda kuch, sprint tezligi, reaksiya vaqti va vertikal sakrash xususiyatlari bo'yicha juda yaxshi holatda. Natijada sprint mashqlari reaksiya vaqtini yaxshilash uchun, vertikal sakrash mashqlari esa kuchni oshirish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin, deb hisoblaymiz.

Gandbolchilarning mavsumoldi mashg'ulotlarini rejalashtirishda buni e'tiborga olish foydali bo'ladi, deb hisoblaymiz.

REFERENCES

- 1.Yarasheva, D. (2024). TYPES AND EFFECTIVENESS OF FITNESS TRAINING. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 299–307. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/28041>
- 2.Yarasheva, D. (2024). SUBJECTIVE AND SPORT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1). Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/28960>
- 3.Yarasheva, D. (2024). SPONSORSHIP RELATIONSHIPS IN SPORTS MARKETING. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 337–345. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29029>
- 4.Dilnoza, Y. (2023). SUB'YEKTIV VA SPORT.
- 5.Dilnoza, Y. (2024). SOG'LOMLASHTIRUVCHI MASHG'ULOTLARNING TURLARI VA SAMARADORLIGI.
- 6.Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). SPORTS PEDAGOGY BASED ON PSYCHOMOTOR AND DEVELOPMENT THEORIES. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 26–41. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-05>
- 7.Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). PHYSIOLOGICAL REACTIONS TO INTERNAL LOAD STUDY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-07>
- 8.Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). SPORTS, CULTURE AND SOCIETY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 152–163. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-17>
- 9.Yarasheva, D. (2024). IN HANDBALL GYMS: SAFE PHYSICAL EXERCISES AND INJURY PREVENTION. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 23 – 32. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30639>
- 10.Yarasheva, D. (2024). USE OF HANDBALL INDUSTRY AND TECHNOLOGY. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 9–Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30575>
- 11.Yarasheva, D. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF ENDURANCE IN HANDBALL. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 4(3), 73–77. Retrieved from <https://internationalbulletins.com/intjour/index.php/ibet/article/view/1406>
- 12.Dilnoza, Y. (2023). GANDBOL MURABBIYLARINING FIKRIGA KO'RA, SPORTCHILARNING KO'RSATKICHLARIGA PSIXOLOGIK TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR. *Research and Publications*, 1(1), 86-100.
- 13.Dilnoza, Y. (2023). FOCUS ON AEROBIC (LI) TYPE OF MOTOR ACTIVITY BASED ON FITNESS PROGRAMS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 81-90.

14. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). METHODS OF ORGANIZING NON-TRADITIONAL FITNESS CLASSES. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 61–72. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-09>
15. Yarashova, D. (2023). THE IMPACT OF PLAYING SPORTS IN EARLY CHILDHOOD ON SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 230–234. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24325>
16. Ярашева, Д. (2023). СТИЛИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ НЕТРАДИЦИОННЫХ ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 19(5), 6-10.
17. Дильноза Ярашева. (2023). ФИТНЕС КАК ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ. *Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies*, 2(283). Retrieved from <https://econferenceseries.com/index.php/icmsss/article/view/1777>
18. Yarasheva, D. (2022). BOLALARDA MASHQ QILISHNING AHAMIYATI. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 19(1), 139-142.
19. Yarashova, D. (2023). STRENGTH TRAINING AND STRENGTH TRAINING IN CHILDREN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 211–215. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24177>
20. Yarasheva Dilnoza Ismail Qizi. (2023). TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL SKILLS IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(10), 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue10-16>
21. Nuriddinov, A. (2023). Sport sotsiologiyasi: uning o'tmishdan hozirgi kungacha rivojlanishi va kelajakka umidlari. *Research and Publications*, 1(1), 74-85.
22. Nuriddinov, A. (2024). IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION AND SPORTS. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 4(3), 78-83.
23. Nuriddinov, A. (2024). A COMPILATION STUDY OF INNOVATION IN SPORT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 346-352.
24. Nuriddinov, A. (2024). KARL MARX AND THE THOUGHTS OF CLASS THEORY ON SPORTS CULTURE. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1).
25. Nuriddinov, A. (2024). THE CONNECTION BETWEEN SPORT AND PHILOSOPHY. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 308-317.
26. Nuriddinov, A. (2023). MANAGING THE PROCESS OF TALENT DEVELOPMENT IN SPORTS ANATASIA. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 121-132.
27. Nuriddinov, A. (2023). PHYSICAL ACTIVITY, HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 189-200.
28. Nuriddinov, A. (2023). Use Of Digital Sports Technologies in Sports Television. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 208-219.
29. Nuriddinov, A. (2023). A STUDY OF THE AGGRESSIVE STATUS OF FOOTBALL FANS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 73-80.
30. Nuriddinov, A. (2023). THE ROLE OF FAIR PLAY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 244-250.

31. Nuriddinov, A., Sayfiyev, H., & Sirojev, S. (2023). WHY FOOTBALL IS THE FIRST SPORT THAT COMES TO MIND TODAY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 200-203.
32. Sirojev, S., Nuriddinov, A., & Sayfiyev, H. (2023). THE CONCEPT AND IMPORTANCE OF SHOOTING SPEED IN VOLLEYBALL. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 187-191.
33. Bahodir o'g'li, N. A. (2023). YEVRIPA MAMLAKATLARIDA YUQORI MALAKALI FUTBOLCHI VA MURABBIYLARNI TEXNIK TAKTIK HARAKATLARINI TADBIQ QILISH METODIKASI. *THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH*, 2(14), 187-189.
34. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). BEHAVIORAL CHARACTERISTICS, PRINCIPLES AND WORKING METHODS OF COACHES. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 50-60.
35. Shoxrux, S. (2023). VOLEYBOLDA OTISH TEZLIGI TUSHUNCHASI VA AHAMIYATI. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(11), 913-917.
36. Sirojev, S. (2023). THE CONCEPT AND IMPORTANCE OF SHOOTING SPEED IN VOLLEYBALL. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 187-191.
37. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). THE CONNECTION BETWEEN SPORTS AND LOGIC. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 97-106.
38. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). APPLICATIONS OF SPORT PSYCHOLOGY IN THE WORLD. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 107-120.
39. Sirojev, S. (2023). TEACHING ACTIVITIES AND PHILOSOPHY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 235-243.
40. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF MUTUAL RESPECT AND KINDNESS IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 215-225.
41. Sirojev, S. (2024). EFFECTS OF SOCIAL PHOBIA ON SPORTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 318-326.
42. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). STUDYING SPORTS PSYCHOLOGY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 176-188.
43. Sirojev, S. (2024). EFFECTS OF WARM-UP AND STRETCHING EXERCISES ON PROPRIOCEPTION AND BALANCE. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 353-361.
44. Fayzullo o'g'li, S. S. (2023). YEVRIPA ITTIFOQI VA SPORT. *International journal of scientific researchers*, 2(2), 7-16.
45. Sirojev, S. (2024). SPORTS MASSAGE. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 4(3), 84-88.
46. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). PANDEMIYA DAVRIDA MOBIL SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH VA FITNES DASTURLARI (PROGRAM). *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(7), 37-42. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/414>
47. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). APPROACHES, BEHAVIORAL CHARACTERISTICS, PRINCIPLES AND METHODS OF WORK OF COACHES AND MANAGERS IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 133-151. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-16>

48. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). GLOBALIZATION AND SPORTS INDUSTRY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 164–182.
49. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). SOCIAL SPORTS MARKETING. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 121–134.
<https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-17>
50. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). RECOVERY STRATEGY IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 135–147.
<https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-18>